

THE ROLE OF CHEMICAL ADDITIVES IN ENHANCING CEMENT AND CONCRETE PERFORMANCE

Kurbanov Zavkiddinjon Khamidulloevich

Phd, associate professor,
Jizzakh Polytechnic Institute

Egamberdiyev Ikhtiyor Bakhtiyor oglu
"ULTRA BETON" LLC Testing Laboratory

E-mail: zavaclash@gmail.com

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17347826>

Abstract: The primary material for the construction of buildings and structures of various purposes is concrete. Chemical additives are used in the preparation of the mortar mix to impart specific properties to the concrete. This paper discusses the various types of additives and their effects on the properties of concrete, such as regulating the setting of concrete, enhancing strength and corrosion resistance, and improving water resistance.

Keywords: Additives, concrete mix, regulation of concrete setting, strength, corrosion resistance, water impermeability.

Introduction: Additives are natural or synthetic chemical products added during the mixing of concrete to influence the properties of the cured concrete. They can regulate the technical properties of mortar mixes and cured concrete. Depending on their primary effects, additives for cement mixes and concrete can be classified into:

- Regulators of concrete mix properties (plasticizers and superplasticizers)
- Regulators of concrete setting (accelerators and retarders)
- Enhancers of strength and corrosion resistance of concrete and reinforced concrete
- Additives imparting special properties to concrete: anti-freezing, ensuring setting at negative temperatures, hydrophobic, water-repellent, and improving adhesive properties.

These enhance the mobility, uniformity, flowability, and time-retaining workability of the concrete mix. While keeping the cement consumption constant, plasticizers allow for a reduction in the water-cement ratio, leading to increased strength, water impermeability, and frost resistance of the concrete.

In the construction industry, two types of superplasticizers are commonly used: sulfonated naphthalene formaldehyde condensate (SNF) and melamine sulfonic acid formaldehyde condensate (SMF). These products are sodium salts of the corresponding sulfonic acids. They are linear anionic polymers with sulfate groups.

Additives are used in cement mixes and concrete to improve various properties, such as increasing frost resistance, water impermeability, reducing stratification during transport, and enhancing workability and processability.

The primary purpose of additives is to increase the air content in the concrete mix compared to a mix without additives, decrease the size of air bubbles, and organize the capillary-porous structure. The incorporation of air into the concrete mix improves workability and increases the frost resistance of the concrete.

These additives, often inorganic salts or organic acid salts, accelerate the setting and hardening of concrete. However, some accelerators may lead to efflorescence on the surface of products and corrosion of reinforcement. Therefore, corrosion-resistant additives like sodium nitrite, sodium tetraborate, sodium bichromate, and sodium tetraborate are used in conjunction with accelerators.

These additives contribute to filling the pores in concrete with insoluble products, aiming to increase the strength and water impermeability. Examples include polyamide resin, aliphatic epoxy resin, iron sulfate, and iron chloride. Substances that lower the freezing point of water and promote the setting of concrete at negative temperatures fall into this category. Examples include sodium nitrite, sodium chloride, and potassium carbonate. Special properties are imparted to the concrete mix using hydrophobic and expanding additives.

Frequently used for their multifunctional action, complex additives can influence several unrelated characteristics of concrete. The application of chemical additives is an independent direction for both intensifying the compaction of concrete mixes and regulating the setting processes. These additives also facilitate the formation of finer crystal structures, enhancing the construction and technical properties of concrete.

Adabiyotlar, References, Литературы:

1. Бердиев, О., Талипов, Н., Курбонов, З., & Болотов, Т. (2023). Development of a formulation for dry cement-adhesive dry building mixtures for ceramic slabs using the addition of spent alumina catalysts. Scientific Collection «InterConf», (180), 407-414.
2. Ганиев, А., & Курбанов, З. (2023). ВЛИЯНИЕ ХИМИЧЕСКИХ ДОБАВОК НА СВОЙСТВА ГИПСОВЫЙ НАЛИВНОЙ ПОЛ. Центральноеазиатский журнал образования и инноваций, 2(10 Part 2), 160-163.
3. Kurbanov, Z., & Artiqqulov, D. (2023). DETERMINATION OF THE CONTENT OF DRY CONSTRUCTION MIXED ON THE BASIS OF LOCAL MARBLE WASTE POWDER. Центральноеазиатский журнал образования и инноваций, 2(9), 104-106.
4. Kurbanov, Z., & Artiqqulov, D. (2023). OPPORTUNITIES TO GET LIGHT SUPPLIES BASED ON COAL WASTE. Центральноеазиатский журнал образования и инноваций, 2(9), 100-103.
5. Талипов, Н., Курбанов, З., & Артыккулов, Д. (2023). ЭФФЕКТИВНЫЕ СУХИЕ СМЕСИ С ПОЛИМЕРНЫМИ ДОБАВКАМИ. Центральноеазиатский журнал образования и инноваций, 2(5), 43-48.
6. Курбонов, З., Эшқулов, Н., & Ортыққулов, Д. (2023). ҚУРУҚ ҚУРИЛИШ ҚОРИШМАЛАРИНИНГ АСОСИЙ ТАРКИБИЙ ҚИСМЛАРИ. Центральноеазиатский журнал образования и инноваций, 2(5), 61-66.
7. Курбанов, З., & Ортыккулов, Д. (2023). ВЫСОКОПРОЧНЫЙ ГИПСОВЫЙ ВЯЖУЩИЙ НА ОСНОВЕ СУЛЬФАТСОДЕРЖАЩЕГО ОТХОДА. Models and methods in modern science, 2(2), 5-12.
8. Parsaeva, N., & Kurbanov, Z. (2023, June). Study of the process of determination of chemically contained water in the concentration of additional cement made on the basis of peroxine waste. In AIP Conference Proceedings (Vol. 2789, No. 1). AIP Publishing.4